

Abstract

Title: Is information on geriatric dosing enough for an appropriate prescription?

Author: Roberto Manfredi

Collaborator: ESR7, EUROAGEISM H2020 project - Jovana Brkić, MSc.

Supervisor: Prof. Stefano Girotti

Assoc. Prof. Daniela Fialová, PharmD., Ph.D.

Institution, workplace: University of Bologna, Department of Pharmacy and Biotechnology FaBiT, Alma Mater Studiorum, Italy

Charles University, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Králové, Department of Social and Clinical Pharmacy

Introduction

Ageing is a physiological and unavoidable process, in which occur changes in the body composition, in the homeostatic control and in pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics for many medications. These age-related changes increase sensitivity of older patients both to drug-related problems and to the occurrence of age-related geriatric syndromes, e.g. instability, falls, cognitive impairments, delirium, etc. In those symptoms it is very difficult to identify the causes. It is known that drugs and particularly polypharmacy might worsen the quality of life in older adults and adverse drug events can be also misinterpreted as geriatric syndromes. This creates a sort of circle, where it is complicated to understand for healthcare professionals which factors are the causes and which are the consequences of wrong treatment.

Potentially inappropriate medications (PIMs) are high-risk medications in geriatric patients that must be prescribed rarely and with a special cautiousness. In fact, discrimination because of the age (ageism) is common in clinical trials where insufficient information is collected on how to appropriately treat older adults and also the lack of information in SPCs and drug formularies (on appropriate geriatric dosages and if medications are considered „PIMs“ in the aged) is a part of such discriminatory practices. The aim of this study was to clarify for how many PIMs a geriatric dosage is stated in official drug information sources, mainly in Summary of Product Characteristics – SPCs and in some drug formularies. It was used for this search a comprehensive list of PIMs from different expert explicit criteria prepared for the European EUROAGEISM H2020 project.

Method

The works on this diploma thesis were divided into theoretical and practical part. In the theoretical part, a review of the current literature was necessary to understand the common problems in drug treatment in older patients, the barriers and strategies how to improve their drug therapy and quality of life.

In the practical part of this diploma thesis, dosages for every PIM (stated on a comprehensive list of PIMs of the EUROAGEISM H2020 project) were searched to understand for which PIMs a specific information on geriatric dosages (single, daily dosages) are available in SPCs and selected drug formularies. The sources of data were mainly AIFA (Agenzia Italiana del Farmaco) and BNF (British National Formulary), for a few cases of PIMs (not approved for clinical use in Europe, but only in the USA) we used also PDR website (Prescriber's Digital Reference – U.S source). In AIFA database there were listed different brand drug products that include a PIM as an active substance or in combination. The aim was to understand if there was a specific dosage range stated for geriatric patients in none SPCs, all SPCs or some SPCs. BNF instead was a formulary when there was only one range or dose. The availability of information on geriatric single and daily dosages was collected and analyzed only for p.o. (per os) medicinal products with some exceptions (in only parenterally administered PIMs).

Results

There were 364 PIMs on the list and every PIM was checked for single dose and daily dose. For single dose drug regimens: 234 (64,3 %) of PIMs had the same stated dosage for middle age and older patients, 61(16,8 %) PIMs had clarified geriatric dosages in all SPCs and 19 (5,20 %) PIMs had clarified geriatric dosages in some SPCs. For daily dose drug regimens: 212 (58,2 %) PIMs had the same dose stated for middle age and geriatric patients, 69 (18,90 %) PIMs had clarified different geriatric dosages in all the SPCs and 33 (9,1%) PIMs had stated different geriatric dosage in some SPCs. For 50 (13,70 %) of PIMs it was impossible to find the exact information on dosage, even for adults.

Conclusion

Only less than 30 % of PIMs have already specified geriatric dosages in SPCs. The majority sources do not clarify the geriatric dose or still emphasize only “start low, go slow” approach - a step-wise dose increase according to clinical response.

It is necessary to conduct studies about specific dosages in geriatric patients in order to decrease side effects of drugs and increase their efficacy in older people; indeed, it was demonstrated by many studies, how only standard (middle-age) approaches or empirical approaches can lead to harmful results. The improvement in quality of life should be the first aim during the treatment process. In order to achieve this purpose, it's necessary to reduce the number of medications prescribed to older adults; in fact, polypharmacy is the first risk factor of PIM use, it increases morbidity and mortality and also the confusion about eventual drug-drug or drug-disease interactions. The process of deprescribing (withdrawal medications or reducing the dose) could be emphasized particularly for PIMs. Regulatory measures (changes in SPCs and inclusion of information on their specific dosages) could simplify this process and implementation of deprescribing strategies. Management of PIMs is also a part of the role of clinical pharmacists in geriatrics (specialists for medication use in older people), who should manage and control appropriate treatments, increase patients' compliance and to discern the origin of negative events related to medications.

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